

ISic3002

I.Sicily inscription 3002

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone (Taormina)

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

found on Ortygia, during demolition of 16th cent fortifications at
entrance to island

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6189

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140306

1. [— — —].[— — — — — — — —]#⁷
2. [— —]ΤΗΣ[— — — — — — — —]Υ
3. [— —]άδα τὰν α ψ, τ [οῦ γ] υναῖκα
4. [— —] καὶ Ἰσει.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645352

Bibliography

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